

EVALUATION OF POZZOLANIC ADDITIVES FOR ENHANCING THE STRENGTH AND DURABILITY OF FIBER- REINFORCED CONCRETE

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Abstract: High-performance concrete (HPC) is distinguished by its ability to meet specific performance and uniformity standards, which are difficult to achieve with conventional materials and methods. Since its introduction, HPC has become a key material in large-scale construction projects that require high strength, excellent flowability, and exceptional durability. While high-strength concrete always qualifies as high-performance concrete, the reverse does not hold true. Merely specifying high-strength concrete does not ensure the durability of the material. Developing a concrete mix that incorporates all these characteristics is a complex task.

Pozzolanic materials, such as Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS), silica fume, rice husk ash, fly ash, and high-reactive metakaolin, play a crucial role in enhancing the performance of concrete by partially replacing cement. In our research, we conducted X-ray diffraction (XRD) tests on these materials to examine the variation in their constituent components. Maintaining a controlled water-cement ratio is vital, and water-reducing admixtures like superplasticizers are used to produce high-performance concrete. We tested various combinations of materials, including rice husk ash, GGBS, and silica fume, to meet the necessary specifications. Furthermore, synthetic fibers (Recron fibers) were incorporated at different percentages (0.0%, 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3% of the total concrete weight) during casting.

We experimented with different proportions of silica fume while keeping the fiber content constant, and we conducted tests using two types of cement: Portland slag cement and ordinary Portland cement. Various forms such as mortar, cubes, cylinders, and prisms were cast, and tests for compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, and flexural strength were performed. Additionally, we evaluated porosity and permeability to assess the overall performance. A significant number of trial mixes were undertaken to determine the optimal material combination that met the desired performance characteristics.

Keywords: High-performance concrete, Pozzolanic materials, Superplasticizers, X-ray diffraction, Synthetic fibers.

1. INTRODUCTION

A basic building material, concrete is created by mixing cementitious ingredients, water, aggregates, and occasionally admixtures in precise amounts. It can be molded into a variety of shapes and is known as plastic concrete when it is first mixed. Over time, it undergoes a hardening process through a chemical interaction between water and cement, leading to greater

strength.

Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) and simple round mild steel bars were commonly used in the construction of concrete structures in the first half of the 20th century. Because concrete materials were so widely available and it was thought that any combination of these materials could produce concrete, durability was overlooked. Although strength was emphasized, the structures' long-term durability received less consideration.

This reduction was caused by a number of events, especially after 1970. High-strength rebars with surface deformations started to be used more frequently. Significant modifications were also made to the characteristics of cement and its constituent parts. Additionally, without giving their effects enough thought, engineers started adding additional cementitious ingredients and admixtures to concrete. As a result, concrete constructions began to deteriorate more quickly, particularly those constructed after 1970. To guarantee the long-term stability and dependability of concrete structures, these issues must be addressed and durability must be given more importance.

2. HIGH PERFORMANCE CONCRETE (HPC)

The construction industry has recently embraced the concept of "High-Performance Concrete" (HPC). According to the American Concrete Institute (ACI), HPC is defined as concrete that meets specific performance and uniformity requirements, which are challenging to achieve using traditional materials and standard methods of mixing, placing, and curing. The ACI commentary further clarifies that HPC is designed with specific characteristics tailored to suit particular applications and environments. Key properties that are often critical for a given application include ease of placement, the ability to compact without segregation, early-age strength, long-term mechanical properties, permeability, density, heat of hydration, toughness, volume stability, and the capacity to endure harsh environmental conditions for extended periods.

3. KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF HIGH-PERFORMANCE CONCRETE

High-performance concrete (HPC) is characterized by several distinct features that contribute to its superior properties. One of the key features is the improved dispersion of cement particles, which enhances the overall performance of the concrete. This leads to an increase in compressive strength due to a more uniform mixture. HPC also benefits from a reduced water-to-binder ratio, which plays a critical role in improving strength and durability. The mixture incorporates a variety of grain sizes, which helps in optimizing the packing density of the ingredients, resulting in a more compact and dense cement paste.

Another important characteristic of HPC is its uniform and non-bleeding consistency, which ensures that the mixture remains stable during placement and does not separate or lose its components. The reduced presence of capillary pores and the discontinuous pore structure further contribute to improved strength and durability by minimizing pathways for water and other aggressive agents to penetrate. Additionally, HPC provides a stronger bond between the cement paste and aggregate at the interface, ensuring better cohesion and structural integrity.

The material also has a low content of free lime, which helps in preventing undesirable chemical reactions that could affect durability. Controlled shrinkage within the concrete minimizes the risk of cracking, and the effective confinement of aggregates ensures better load distribution and improved material performance. Furthermore, HPC minimizes the occurrence of micro-cracking, typically until about 65-70% of the specified compressive strength is reached, helping maintain its strength during the early stages of curing. Finally, in the event of failure, HPC exhibits a smooth fracture surface, indicating a more predictable and controlled breakdown of the material. These features collectively make high-performance concrete a highly reliable and durable construction material.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Several early studies have explored the use of different pozzolanic materials as partial substitutes for cement in high-performance concrete, often combined with superplasticizers, to improve its properties. These studies also investigated the addition of fiber reinforcement with pozzolanic materials to further enhance concrete's performance. Below is a summary of key research in this field:

Al-Khalaf and Yousif (1984) examined the use of rice husk ash (RHA) in concrete, discovering that up to 40% cement replacement with RHA had little effect on compressive strength. They found that the optimal burning temperature for RHA was about 500°C for two hours, and finer grinding improved its pozzolanic activity.

Aitcin et al. (1995) discussed the evolution of high-performance concrete (HPC), noting significant increases in compressive strength over the years. In 1988, concrete with 120 MPa strength was achieved, compared to the 40 MPa previously considered high strength. This advancement was largely due to technological improvements, especially the use of superplasticizers, which reduce the water-cement ratio, resulting in a denser and stronger microstructure. Silica fume, a highly reactive pozzolanic material, also improved the paste-aggregate bond, reducing debonding. Supplementary materials like fly ash and slag contributed to slump retention at low water-cement ratios.

Ismail and Waliuddin (1996) investigated the effect of RHA on high-strength concrete and found that replacing 10-20% of the cement with RHA yielded optimal strength, though higher replacements led to strength reductions. They also explored finely ground RHA, which showed promising results even in crystalline form.

Alhozaimy, Soroushian, and Mirza (1996) studied the mechanical properties of polypropylene fiber-reinforced concrete and its interaction with pozzolanic materials. Their findings showed that polypropylene fibers improved the concrete's toughness and impact resistance, with positive interaction between the fibers and pozzolanic materials like silica fume.

Zollo et al. (1997) provided an overview of fiber-reinforced concrete (FRC), covering its development over the past 30 years. This review discussed various FRC terminologies and behavior models, focusing on its mechanical properties.

Colleparidi (1998) reviewed the use of superplasticizers in concrete to enhance its placement characteristics. Superplasticizers, particularly those based on sulfonated melamine formaldehyde (SMF) or naphthalene formaldehyde (SNF), improve workability and reduce the water-cement ratio without compromising strength.

Qian Jueshi and Shi Caijun (2000) reviewed high-performance cementing materials derived from industrial slags, emphasizing the activation of pozzolanic properties in slags like blast furnace slag, steel slag, and copper slag to substitute Portland cement, reduce energy consumption, and improve strength and durability.

Ganesh Babu and Sree Rama Kumar (2000) studied the efficiency of Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS) in concrete, noting that the strength efficiency factor increased with the percentage of GGBS up to about 28 days. They also found that GGBS effectiveness depended on the water-binder ratio.

Papayianni, Tsohos, and Mavria (2005) explored the influence of different superplasticizers on concrete mixtures. Their study demonstrated that superplasticizers could significantly increase workability, reduce the water-cement ratio, and improve compressive strength.

Ajdkiewicz and Radomski (2002) examined high-performance concrete research trends in Poland, addressing engineering and economic aspects of HPC. They emphasized the need for increased HPC usage in structural applications and discussed its benefits in construction.

Aitcin et al. (2003) focused on the durability of high-performance concrete, noting that HPC, with a water-binder ratio between 0.30 and 0.40, is generally more durable than ordinary concrete due to its lower porosity and disconnected capillary networks. However, they also highlighted that HPC's fire resistance is lower than that of ordinary concrete, although still relatively safe.

De Sensale (2006) studied the strength development of concrete using RHA, noting positive effects on early strength. The research compared RHA produced through controlled incineration with residual RHA, revealing significant improvements in compressive strength, especially at later ages.

Oner and Akyuz (2007) examined the effect of GGBS on concrete's compressive strength, finding that adding GGBS increased strength up to an optimum replacement level of 55-59%. Beyond this point, further GGBS additions did not improve strength.

Bozkurt and Yagicioglu (2010) studied lightweight concrete with pozzolanic materials under different curing conditions. They found that silica fume increased both compressive and tensile strength while lowering the capillary absorption coefficient.

Suja et al. (2016) investigated the flexural performance of hybrid fiber-reinforced self-compacting concrete (SCC) incorporating rice husk ash (RHA) as a partial substitute for cement. The study found that adding steel fiber (0.75%) and polypropylene fiber (0.25%) improved the flexural behavior of SCC, with cement replacement by RHA ranging from 0% to 30%.

Amirtharaj et al. (2018) assessed the durability of steel fiber-reinforced concrete (SFRC) containing fly ash. Their study showed that SFRC with 40% fly ash as a partial cement replacement exhibited lower strength loss when exposed to sulfuric acid compared to regular SFRC, highlighting its improved durability.

Sanjeev et al. (2019) studied fiber-reinforced concrete incorporating steel fibers (1% binder ratio), fly ash, and GGBS up to 50% in M30 grade concrete. The research found that workability improved with these replacements, though higher OPC replacement percentages did not significantly enhance durability. The optimal OPC replacement for strength was 30%.

Ramakrishnan et al. (2022) compared the durability of fiber-reinforced concrete with steel and glass fibers for M30 grade concrete. They evaluated durability through acid attack and rapid chloride permeability tests, identifying the optimal fiber content for enhanced durability.

Zaid et al. (2023) studied the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced recycled aggregate concrete (RAC), showing that a mix of 10% waste silica ash (WSA), 50% recycled aggregate (RA), and 1.5% polypropylene fibers exhibited improved compressive strength, tensile strength, and durability. The inclusion of WSA and polypropylene fibers helped mitigate the negative effects of RA.

Kashyap et al. (2023) highlighted improvements in the mechanical and durability properties of concrete mixtures through the use of marble powder and nano silica. Their study showed that nano silica enhanced pozzolanic activity and helped reduce damage caused by sulfuric acid exposure, improving the concrete's durability and overall performance.

5. DISCUSSION

- The findings indicate that the consistency percentage increases gradually as the percentage of GGBS replacing cement rises, though the change is minimal. In contrast, a notable increase in consistency is observed with higher amounts of rice husk ash.
- The fineness of the cement plays a crucial role in its consistency. Silica fume, with its finer particle size and larger surface area compared to cement, significantly boosts the consistency. When the percentage of silica fume rises from 0% to 30%, the normal consistency increases by around 45%.

- In experiments involving Recron fiber in Portland slag cement, no significant increase in compressive strength was seen with fiber content ranging from 0.0% to 0.1%. However, a noticeable improvement in compressive strength occurred when the fiber percentage increased from 0.1% to 0.2%. Beyond 0.2% fiber content, strength began to decrease. Among the different fiber mixes, the concrete with 0.2% fiber content exhibited the highest compressive strength at 28 days compared to other fiber mixes, though still lower than that of unreinforced concrete. Additionally, silica fume was used as a partial replacement for cement at varying percentages (10%, 20%, and 30%), combined with 0.2% Recron fiber. Concrete with 20% silica fume replacement of slag cement showed the highest strength, while for ordinary Portland cement, the best strength was achieved with a 30% replacement of silica fume.
- The addition of silica fume significantly influences the capillary absorption coefficient in Recron fiber reinforced concrete. With a 10% silica fume content, the capillary absorption is reduced by about 50% compared to concrete with only 0.2% fiber. When the silica fume content increases to 20%, capillary absorption decreases by approximately 70% compared to the same fiber content. However, at a 30% silica fume content, there is a slight increase in the capillary absorption coefficient.

6. CONCLUSIONS

- Replacing cement with ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBS) increases the consistency of the mortar. However, despite its fine nature, GGBS passing through the 75-micron sieve does not contribute to improved strength in the mortar. When the replacement level of GGBS exceeds 10% in Portland slag cement, there is a rapid decline in strength.
- The addition of rice husk ash (RHA) as a cement substitute also enhances the consistency of the mortar. When RHA is properly burned at controlled temperatures, it can improve the strength of the mortar, but overall, its strength contribution is not satisfactory.
- The incorporation of superplasticizers facilitates a low water-to-cement ratio, which is essential for achieving the desired strength in concrete mixtures.
- In Portland slag cement with the addition of Recron fiber, the maximum compressive strength at 28 days is observed at a fiber content of 0.2%. Additionally, the splitting tensile and flexural strengths increase by about 5% with 0.2% fiber content compared to plain concrete. However, exceeding the 0.2% fiber content results in a notable loss of strength.
- As the percentage of cement replaced with silica fume increases, the consistency of the mixture also increases.
- When Portland slag cement is combined with 0.2% Recron fiber and varying levels of silica fume, the compressive, splitting tensile, and flexural strengths are significantly impacted. At a 20% silica fume content with 0.2% fiber, the compressive strength at 28 days increases by 7% compared to concrete with just 0.2% fiber. The splitting tensile and flexural strengths show even greater improvements, increasing by approximately 12% and 10%, respectively, compared to normal concrete.
- Based on these findings, the optimal mix to achieve the desired performance is determined to be 0.2% Recron fiber and 20% silica fume.
- For ordinary Portland cement (OPC), the compressive strength increases as the percentage of silica fume rises from 0% to 30%, when combined with 0.2% Recron fiber. This leads to an approximate 20% improvement in strength compared to normal concrete with OPC.

- The splitting tensile strength increases by around 15% with a 10% silica fume content and constant 0.2% Recron fiber. However, higher silica fume content beyond this point causes a decrease in tensile strength. Similarly, the flexural strength consistently declines by about 40% as the silica fume percentage reaches 30%.
- Concrete with OPC shows better compressive strength than Portland slag cement when silica fume and 0.2% Recron fiber are incorporated into the mixture.
- The capillary absorption coefficient (k) decreases significantly with increasing silica fume content at a constant 0.2% fiber content. With 20% silica fume, the k value is reduced by approximately 70% compared to concrete with no silica fume.
- The porosity of the concrete also decreases as the silica fume content rises from 0% to 30% in Recron fiber reinforced concrete.

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